

Methods Of Developing Problem Educational Competence Of Future Higher Education Teachers

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Abstract: *The article discusses the nature, content, basic concepts and categories of problem-based teaching and its role in increasing the knowledge activity of students in the system of higher professional education.*

Keywords — Concept of problem-based learning, cognitive activity, cognitive difficulties, problem situation, problem, problem-based task, problem-based presentation lecture, problem-based teaching lecture, joint problem-based lecture, problem-based seminar session classes.

INTRODUCTION.

At the root of the reforms implemented in the education system of our country, the most important problem is raising the young generation who are proactive in professional activity. Regarding the analysis of the pedagogical-psychological aspects of the development of educational-cognitive competence of pre-service military education teachers as a pedagogical concept, we will first analyze our approach by referring to the scientific opportunities in the work of local and foreign researchers.

As we dwell on the content-essence of the pedagogical-psychological aspects of the concept of development of educational-cognitive competence of teachers: it is necessary to dwell on the etymological analysis of the concepts of "competence", "competence". Scientists have interpreted the concepts of "competence" and "competence" differently. Competency approach means, first of all, the word "Competence" comes from the word "to compete", which means "knowledge in this or that field".

Based on the popular associative-reflexive education concept, problem-based education was developed. It is a set of tools that allows students to creatively participate in learning the educational material, as well as to develop their knowledge.

The main categories of this type of training are problem situation, problem and problem task.

A problem situation is considered as a cognitive challenge, in order to overcome it, students need to acquire new knowledge or perform mental actions. If such a situation is accepted by students as a solution, it becomes a problem for them. And the problem, in turn, becomes a problematic task with a deliberately limited space for the search for a solution when there are parameters and conditions to solve.

Such a specially formed set of tasks should be the basis for the implementation of the main function of problem-based education, which consists of a creative approach to mastering educational material and gaining experience in independent creative activity.

This type of teaching implies a certain system of problematic situations, problems and problematic tasks that correspond to the cognitive abilities and capabilities of students.

Accordingly, different levels of problem solving are used in the learning process.

At the first stage, the teacher himself analyzes the problem situation, identifies the problem, sets the task and directs the students to solve it independently.

Second, at the higher level, the teacher analyzes the situation together with the students and leads them to the problem, and they independently identify the problem and begin to solve it.

In the third stage, which is considered the highest, the teacher defines the problem situation and brings it to the attention of the students, then the students analyze it, identify the problem and look for a rational solution themselves.

Correctly formulating the problem and turning it into a chain of clear and specific problem tasks is the key to success in problem solving.

In addition, the intellectual search process is associated with assumptions and assumptions about the possible solution to the problem. Then assumptions and assumptions take the form of hypotheses, that is, sufficiently justified didactic assumptions, which in turn are confirmed or not confirmed in practice. This is a general scheme of problem-based learning, which not only teaches students how to correctly solve a specific educational problem, but also provides them with the opportunity to gain meaningful experience and relevant knowledge, which makes learning takes the main place in the process.

Such training has a number of advantages:

- teaches logical, scientific, creative thinking;
- teaches to independently search for the necessary knowledge and makes the educational material more interesting and evidence-based;

- teaches students to overcome intellectual difficulties and awakens in them a positive emotional attitude to mastering new educational material;
- consolidates mastering of educational material and helps turn knowledge into beliefs;
- forms students' cognitive interests and develops creative cognitive abilities.

Lectures, seminars and practical exercises, laboratory work are widely used types of educational activities in order to increase the cognitive activity of students in the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions.

It is known that mastering the educational material begins with the lecture. However, a monologue lecture devoid of discussion elements and problematic questions does not interest students today. Experience shows that there is an activation of the students' cognitive activity in the lecture, the teacher does not simply announce the main rules of the educational material, but constantly argues, reflects, sometimes as if arguing with himself, the students leads to the analysis of conflicting opinions, different points of view and involves them in their thinking.

There is a certain typology of such lectures, for example:

- a lecture given using more problematic issues and contradictions as educational material. In didactics, this is called problem presentation lectures;
- lectures in which a large part of the educational material is presented to students for independent (partial or complete) mastery by solving problematic issues. Such lectures are called problem-based learning lectures;
- lectures that combine the elements of the first and second types of lectures. They are usually called integrated problem lectures.

Its essence is that the teacher explains the educational material, formulates the problems, focuses the students' attention on their importance and reveals their internal contradictions.

During the lessons, the main rules of the educational material should be mastered by solving the problems posed by the teacher and the students themselves. The teacher's role in the lecture is to set problems and organize their independent solution by students. At the same time, educational material aimed at updating the existing knowledge necessary for the current lecture is provided, and the necessary supporting information is also provided. Within the framework of this material, the lecturer sets before the students problematic questions, tasks or other tasks that require the activation of independent, creative, mental activity of the students within certain limits. It should be noted that in such lessons, problematic questions and assignments are combined with various informational questions that guide students to a rational solution and require evidence. It should be noted that in such lessons, problematic questions and assignments are combined with various informational questions that guide students to a rational solution and require evidence. But this

requires the teacher to have certain skills, to be able to create problematic situations, to identify problems, to set problematic tasks, to be able to direct the intellectual potential of students to solve them.

It is clear that it is impossible to organize and conduct such lectures on all subjects of the training course. This is due to differences in the nature and structure of the educational material. In addition, an important condition for the successful and effective conduct of such lectures is sufficient readiness and interest of students. Experience shows that it is appropriate to conduct such lectures in junior classes and senior courses.

The didactic combination of the lectures under consideration is called a combined problem lecture, during which the problem presentation of the material is combined with its problem acquisition.

A didactic combination of discussed lectures is called a combined problem lecture, in which the problem presentation of the material is combined with its problem assimilation. That is, in such a lecture, the teacher uses the elements of the first two types of problem lectures. Taking into account the characteristics of a particular educational material, the level of preparation of students and their previous experience in such a lecture, the teacher has the opportunity to significantly expand the options for making it problematic.

Seminars are one of the important means of increasing students' cognitive activity. On the one hand, they are a means of more meaningful collective consideration of the most important educational problems, and on the other hand, they provide an opportunity to discuss real problems that have arisen and arouse interest in students to participate in discussions. The seminar serves to form the experience of students' intellectual activity, increase their creative independence and develop their rhetorical skills during the educational process.

Seminar sessions are held to discuss, deepen and strengthen previously acquired knowledge, as well as to master new educational material.

At the same time, problem seminars are widely used in practice. It is more relevant for humanities and social sciences, where students study the laws of social development and the nature of modern socio-economic and socio-political processes.

The topic of such a seminar is presented to students in the form of a problem that does not have a clear and quick solution. Therefore, in the process of preparing for the lesson, the teacher develops his scenario in detail, which, as a rule, includes:

- describe methods of updating knowledge necessary for students to participate in the upcoming discussion;
- boundaries of problem formulation and solution;
- formation of separate problems, the solution of which provides the entire solution of the problem;

- predict possible points of view, facts and arguments in the discussion of the problem;
- formation of final conclusions and problematic issues that can be the subject of further discussions.

Practice shows that such seminars, on the one hand, require thorough didactic preparation (topics of problematic issues, collection of necessary facts and evidence, etc.), and on the other hand, formation of emotional and cognitive interest of seminar participants and discussion mood. This means that during the lesson you will:

- to ensure that students freely express and justify their methodological and ideological positions within the framework of the problems set during the seminar;
- to ensure the interested participation of students in the discussion of the issues under consideration;
- formation of students' skills to critically analyze, clarify and add to the opinions expressed;
- development of agreed reasonable positions on the results of discussion of the main problems of the seminar.

The discussion, as a rule, ends with the formation of general conclusions containing the necessary answers to the questions. However, sometimes not all problematic issues can be solved during the current lesson. This means that it is necessary to identify problematic questions, the answers of which will be the topic of further seminars or the result of independent work of students.

Other types of educational activities in which problem-based learning is widely used are practical exercises, laboratory work and practicals, in which the popular concept of problem-based learning serves as a didactic framework. The strengths of this concept are:

first, to preserve and dialectically harmonize the advantages of other teaching concepts;

secondly, the presence of interdependent requirements for both the teacher's activity and the independent work of students.

The content of this concept includes the consideration and implementation of two main principles, according to which learning is considered as a joint activity of the teacher and students.

The first is the principle of active development of the individual during training. He assumes:

- clear orientation of the education and training system to the formation of a future specialist with a creative way of thinking, scientific erudition, and the required professional competence;
- repeating the main realities of modern social development in the educational process: dynamism, versatility and inconsistency;
- to ensure effective relations between the educational system of young people and their future professional activities;

- purposefully arming students with a research way of thinking, the skills of rational organization of their activities, the need for constant self-improvement.

The second is the problem principle. He assumes:

- study of all phenomena and processes in their continuous development, in close connection and interaction with other phenomena and processes. Future specialists should be able to see all the diversity and inconsistency of the real processes of social development and scientific and technical development in their professional activities;
- training in sufficient cognitive difficulties, providing emotional and aesthetic appeal of independent creative activity;
- development of discussion forms of teaching. Each lesson should ensure the implementation of effective joint activities of the teacher and students, develop students' skills in scientific prediction and finding ways to solve modern problems.

Thus, problem-based learning as an active form of cognitive activity significantly increases students' creative abilities and develops interest in independent search for necessary educational and scientific information [3; 4].

It is known that problem-based education is the most complex didactic process of forming the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities of students. Unlike traditional forms of education, it is associated with certain didactic conditions, the implementation of which can speak about its success and effectiveness. Such conditions should include:

- creating intellectual challenges that match the students' knowledge and abilities;
- purposefully arming students with the necessary knowledge to freely guide them to the scientific content of problematic situations;
- formation of necessary skills and competencies in both theoretical and practical areas of students' future activities in solving problematic issues.

This is the main content of the concepts of problem-based and problem-based education, and its main goal is to develop students' intellectual and creative abilities.

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